
**ANALYTIC OF BRAND IMAGE, COMPANY IMAGE, AND PRICE ON
PURCHASING DECISIONS AND THEIR IMPLICATIONS ON
CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF MEDICAL DEVICES PRODUCTS IN
JABODETABEK AT PT. MDT**

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Abstract:

This study aims to analyze the effect of Brand Image, Company Image, and Price on Purchasing Decisions and Their Implications on Customer Satisfaction of Medical Device Products in Jabodetabek at PT. MDT. Competition in the business world today is getting tougher and companies must have a vision and mission that must be maintained so that customers and partners or company colleagues do not turn away. The population in this study were customers of PT. MDT Jabodetabek Region. The sampling technique in this study the author uses a saturated sampling method. The analytical method used is path analysis. The data analysis used in this study is assisted by the SPSS Version 23. The results of this study indicate that (1) Corporate Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions, (2) Brand Image does not significantly influence Purchasing Decisions, (3) Price positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions, (4) Purchase Decisions have a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction, and (5) Corporate Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions and their implications for Customer Satisfaction.

Keywords: Brand Image; Company Image; Price; Purchasing Decision; Customer Satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

Health equipment is a supporting facility in the world of health, many hospitals and health companies need medical devices. Medical equipment production companies are now increasingly being found. In an effort to maintain the continuity of its business in Indonesia, PT. MDT continues to improve performance with its main goal is to increase customer satisfaction. To find out these factors, researchers conducted initial Pre-research conducted by researchers by interviewing 50 customers

Source: Pre-Research Results (2018)

Figure 1: Priority Scale Order in Buying Products

Based on Figure 1, it is known that most of the customer factors in deciding to buy medical devices, especially medical devices, are Corporate Image and Brand Image. In addition, prices are the next factor that is considered by customers.

In addition, there are differences in the results of research in previous studies (research gaps). Research conducted by Wijaya shows that Price has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction [1]. This is in contrast to the research conducted by Bayuningsari and Dion that Price does not have a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction [2]. Other research conducted by Hasanuddin shows that Price influences Customer Satisfaction through Purchasing Decisions as an Intervening variable [3].

Research conducted by Saad and Ahmad [4] and Ene And Betul [5] showed that Corporate Image had a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. This contrasts with the research conducted by Bernadus that Corporate Image has no significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.

Based on the results of the Pre-research shown as well as the research gap in previous studies, in this case the author needs to do deeper research to be able to prove whether there is a significant influence of these 3 (three) factors on Customer Satisfaction with the Purchase Decision as an Intervening Variable.

In accordance with the background of the research stated above, the researcher formulated the research problem to be discussed. The following is the formulation of the problem in this study:

- 1) Does Corporate Image affect the Purchasing Decision of Customers PT. MDT?
- 2) Does Brand Image affect the Purchasing Decision of Customers PT. MDT?
- 3) Does the price affect the Customer Purchase Decision PT. MDT?
- 4) Does the Purchase Decision affect the Customer Satisfaction PT. MDT?
- 5) Does Corporate Image affect the Purchasing Decision and its implications with Customer Satisfaction PT. MDT?

2. Literature Review

Buying Decision

According to Schiffman and Kanuk, purchasing decisions are the process of selecting two or more alternative choices that result in a decision to buy or not buy [6]. Alternative choices must be available when consumers will make a decision.

Purchasing decisions are the process by which consumers decide which brand to buy. Consumers will buy the most preferred brand, but can be influenced by two factors that are between purchase intentions and purchasing decisions, namely the attitude of others and unexpected situations. The purchase intention can change if the situation faced by the consumer impedes or forces to cancel the purchase or switch to another alternative.

According to Kotler and Armstrong, purchasing decisions made by consumers have a structure [7]. Structure of purchasing decisions include:

- 1) Decision about the type of product. Consumers can make decisions to buy a product. Consumers have an interest in buying products and considering other product alternatives.
- 2) Decisions about the shape of the product. Consumers will consider size, quality, style and so on. Companies must pay attention to consumer preferences for the product concerned in order to maximize the power of the product brand.
- 3) Decisions about sellers. Consumers will decide where the product will be purchased so the company must pay attention to how consumers choose a particular seller.
- 4) Decision about the number of products. Consumers can make decisions about how many products to buy at a time. Companies need to prepare the number of products according to the wishes of different consumers.
- 5) Decision about the time of purchase. Consumers can make decisions about when the product must be purchased so the company must know the factors that influence consumption decisions in determining the time of purchase.

Hawkins, et al. Gave different opinions. The initial stage of the consumer is awareness of need recognition, information search (information search), then evaluation of alternatives prior to purchase (pre-purchase alternative evaluation), after which a purchase is made, then consumption and at the final stage of the buyer will show satisfaction or dissatisfaction [8]. The buying decision stage includes:

- 1) Introduction to the Problem. The introduction of a problem is the first stage in the purchasing decision process where consumers recognize a problem or need. Consumers are aware of a difference between the actual situation and the conditions they want. These needs can be driven by stimuli from within consumers or from outside.
- 2) Information Search. Consumers have the urge to fulfill their needs so that consumers will find information about products that can satisfy their needs. Information retrieval by consumers depends on how much information needs about the products needed.
- 3) Alternative Assessment / Alternative Evaluation. Consumers use information to evaluate alternative brands in making purchasing decisions and will try to find satisfaction. Consumers will evaluate alternatives obtained from information search

results, consumers can pay more attention to products that provide benefits sought or expected by consumers. The evaluation process that needs to be known to consumers is knowledge about product class attributes and trademark beliefs that can influence consumers in determining attitudes toward brands.

- 4) Purchasing Decisions. At the evaluation stage, consumers arrange their brands in the set of choices and form purchase intentions and will choose brands that consumers like. But there are also factors that influence like other people and unexpected circumstances.
- 5) Behavior After Purchasing. After making a purchase of a product the consumer will experience some level of satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Satisfaction after purchase experienced by consumers based on consumer expectations of information received by consumers receive about the product. If products that have been purchased by consumers meet expectations, then consumers will feel satisfied.

Customer Satisfaction

From all activities carried out by a company, it will ultimately lead to the value that will be given by the customer regarding perceived satisfaction. Satisfaction is a level of feeling where someone states the results of a comparison of the product (service) performance that is received and expected [9].

Lovelock and Jochen stated that customer satisfaction is as a after-purchase evaluation, where perceptions of the performance of selected product / service alternatives meet or exceed expectations before purchase [10]. If the perception of performance cannot meet expectations, what happens is dissatisfaction.

Kotler identified 4 (four) methods for measuring customer satisfaction, namely:

- 1) System of Complaints and Suggestions. Customer-oriented service companies must provide the widest opportunity for customers to submit their suggestions, criticisms, opinions and complaints. Media that can be used in the form of comment cards, toll-free telephone lines and others.
- 2) Ghost Shopping. One way to get an overview of customer satisfaction is to hire a number of ghostshoppers to act as potential customers of company services and competitors. They will report on the strengths and weaknesses of company services compared to competitors.
- 3) Lost Customer Analysis. Companies can contact customers who have stopped buying or have switched to other companies, in order to understand why this happened and can take further improvement and refinement policies.
- 4) Customer Satisfaction Survey. Most studies can use survey methods either via post, telephone, email or direct interviews.

Corporate Image

Talking about the image (image), usually involves the image of the product, company, brand, party, person or whatever is formed in someone's mind. according to Zeithaml and Gremler image is the emission or reproduction of identity or the form of individuals, objects or organizations [11].

Furthermore, Jefkins and Yadin said that there are 5 types of images namely [12]:

- 1) Shadow image (mirror image). this image is attached to an insider or member of the organization (usually a leader) regarding the outside party's assumptions about the organization.
- 2) Applicable image (current image). is an image or view adopted by external parties regarding an organization.
- 3) Expected image (wish image). is an image desired by management.
- 4) Corporate image (corporate image). is the image of an organization as a whole, so it's not just an image of its products and services.
- 5) Multiple images (multiple images). the large number of employees (individuals), branches, or representatives of a company or organization can bring up an image that is not necessarily the same as the organization or company as a whole.

Warren argues, understanding that comes from incomplete information produces an imperfect image. In addition, complete information about the company's image includes the following four elements:

- 1) Personality. The overall characteristics of the company are understood by the target public such as companies that can be trusted, companies that have social responsibility.
- 2) Reputation. The things that have been done by the company and are believed by the target are based on their own experience or other parties such as the security performance of a bank transaction.
- 3) Value. The values of a company in other words a corporate culture such as management's attitude that cares about customers, employees who are responsive to customer requests and complaints
- 4) Corporate Identity. Components that make it easier to introduce public targets to companies such as logos, colors and slogans.

Brand Image

The use of a brand or brand reflects the identity of the product or service offered by the seller. Brands also have a role in identifying sources or product makers that allow consumers to evaluate similar products differently depending on how the brand itself.

Sulistiyari said that brand image is a description of the association of consumer confidence in a particular brand [13]. Supranto and Limakrisma state brand image is what consumers think and feel when they hear or see a brand and what consumers learn about brands [14]. So it can be concluded that brand image is a set of brand associations that consumers can feel and think about that are created and maintained by marketers to form in the minds of consumers.

According to Sciffman and Kanuk, there are several factors forming brand image, as follows:

- 1) Quality and quality, related to the quality of goods products offered by manufacturers with certain brands.
- 2) Reliable or reliable, related to opinions or agreements formed by the community about a product consumed.
- 3) Use or benefit, which is related to the function of a product that can be used by consumers.
- 4) Services, which are related to the task of producers in serving their customers.
- 5) Risks, related to the size due to profits and losses that may be experienced by consumers.

- 6) Prices, which in this case relate to high or low levels of the amount of money spent by consumers to influence a product, can also affect long-term images.
- 7) Image owned by the brand itself, namely in the form of views, agreements, and information relating to a brand of a particular product.

Alma mentions indicators of brand image, among others [15]:

- 1) The level of physical attributes is to recognize the brand name, logo or brand symbol.
- 2) The level of the Functional implication is the risk or benefit to be obtained.
- 3) The psychosocial implication is feeling happy and comfortable when wearing it.

Price

Pricing is one of the important aspects in the company's activities in selling products or services. Good pricing must be in accordance with the quality provided. According to Swastha the price is the amount of money (plus several items if possible) needed to obtain a number of combinations of goods and their servants [16]. Price or tariff is an important component of a product or service, because it will affect the profit of the producer.

The purpose of pricing according to Harini is as follows [17]:

- 1) Pricing to achieve income on investment. Usually the percentage of the profit from an investment has been determined and to achieve it, a certain price determination of the goods produced is needed.
- 2) Pricing for price stability. This is usually done for companies that happen to be in control of prices. Price control efforts are directed primarily to prevent price wars from occurring, especially when faced with declining demand.
- 3) Pricing to maintain or increase its share in the market. If the company gets a market share with a certain area, then it must try to maintain it or even develop it. For this reason, policy in pricing must not harm the business of maintaining or developing this part of the market.
- 4) Pricing to deal with or prevent competition. If a new company tries to enter the market with the aim of knowing at what price it will set sales. This means that he has no purpose in setting the price of the trial.
- 5) Determining prices to maximize profits. This goal is usually a model for every business. It seems that profit-seeking businesses have unpleasant connotations as if oppressing consumers. Even though it's actually only natural. Every effort to survive requires profit. Indeed, theoretically prices can develop without limits.

Figure 2: Research Framework

Based on the theoretical review of the literature review, the results of previous studies and the above framework, the following are the hypotheses the authors compiled, namely:

- 1) It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between Corporate Image on Purchasing Decisions
- 2) It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between Brand Image and Purchase Decisions
- 3) It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between the Price of the Purchasing Decision
- 4) It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between the Purchase Decision on Customer Satisfaction
- 5) It is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence between Corporate Image on Purchase Decisions and their implications with Customer Satisfaction

3. Materials and Methods

The type of research used for this study was to use descriptive analytic research. Descriptive research methods have the purpose of making descriptions, drawings, or paintings systematically, factually and accurately regarding the facts, characteristics and relationships between the phenomena investigated.

Data obtained using quantitative data that are structured, using a Likert scale 1-5, from very agree to disagree. In this study examines the Effect of Corporate Image, Brand Image, and Price on Purchase Decisions and Their Implications on Customer Satisfaction PT. MDT.

The population in this study were customers of PT. MDT Jabodetabek Region. The sampling technique in this study the author uses a saturated sampling method.

Data analysis has the purpose of conveying and limiting inventions to become regular and structured data and more meaningful. Data analysis carried out is quantitative analysis expressed by numbers and calculations using standard methods that are assisted with the SPSS Version 23 program.

4. Results and Discussions

At the beginning of the questionnaire there are several fields that show. general description of respondents' answers to the proposed variables along with their dimensions. The following is the descriptive statistics of the research variables.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Variable Corporate Image

Dimensi	Rata-Rata	Min	Max
<i>Personality</i> Perusahaan (CI1)	4,34	3	5
<i>Reputation</i> (CI2)	4,52	2	5
<i>Value/ Nilai Budaya</i> (CI3)	4,48	2	5
<i>Corporate Identity</i> (CI4)	4,44	2	5
Rata-Rata <i>Corporate Image</i>	4,44		

Source: Questionnaire, Data Processed (2018)

Based on table 1, it is known that the average respondent gives a 4.42 rating on Corporate Image owned by PT. MDT. This shows that the company image that is owned is good according to the customer. The highest Corporate Image dimension is 4.52 obtained by Reputation (CI2). While the lowest Corporate Image is 4.34 obtained by Corporate Personality (CI1).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Variable Brand Image

Dimensi	Rata-Rata	Min	Max
<i>Physical Attributes</i> (BI1)	4,44	2	5
<i>Functional Implication</i> (BI2)	4,38	3	5
<i>Psychosocial Implication</i> (BI3)	4,52	2	5
Rata-Rata <i>Brand Image</i>	4,44		

Source: Questionnaire, Data Processed (2018)

Based on table 2, it is known that the average respondent gives a 4.44 assessment of the Brand Image owned by PT. MDT. This shows that respondents have a good perception of the Product Image so far. The highest Brand Image dimension is 4.52 obtained by Psychosocial Implication (BI3) and the lowest Brand Image dimension is 4.38 obtained by Functional Implication (BI2).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Variable Price

Dimensi	Rata-Rata	Min	Max
<i>Keterjangkauan</i> Harga (H1)	4,58	3	5
<i>DayaSaing</i> Harga (H2)	4,42	3	5
<i>Kesesuaian</i> Hargadengan Hasil (H3)	4,54	3	5
Rata-Rata <i>Harga</i>	4,51		

Source: Questionnaire, Data Processed (2018)

Based on table 3, it is known that the average respondent gives a rating of 4.51 to the price set by PT. MDT. This shows that consumers are satisfied with the current price even though they have not given a very good assessment. The lowest price dimension is 4.42 obtained by Price Competitiveness (H2). Whereas the highest dimension of 4.58 was obtained Affordability Price (H1).

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Variable Buying Decision

Dimensi	Rata-Rata	Min	Max
Pengenalan masalah (KP1)	4,56	3	5
Pencarian Informasi (KP2)	4,60	3	5
Penilaian Alternatif (KP3)	4,60	3	5
Membeli (KP4)	4,62	3	5
Perilaku setelah Pembelian (KP5)	3,60	1	5
Rata-Rata Keputusan Pembelian	4,62		

Source: Questionnaire, Data Processed (2018)

Based on table 4, it is known that the average respondent gives a rating of 4.62 to the Purchase Decision. This shows that the customer decides to purchase PT. MDT. The highest Purchase Decision dimension is 4.62 obtained Buying (KP4). While the lowest dimension of 3.60 was obtained after Behavior of Purchase (KP5).

Table-5: Descriptive Statistics of Variable Customer Satisfaction

Dimensi	Rata-Rata	Min	Max
Kualitas Produk (CS1)	4,56	2	5
Pelayanan sesuai Harapan (CS2)	4,58	3	5
Minat Pembelian Ulang (CS3)	4,52	3	5
Rata-Rata Kepuasan Pelanggan	4,55		

Source: Questionnaire, Data Processed (2018)

Based on table 5, it is known that the average respondent gives a 4.55 rating of customer satisfaction. This shows that customers have good satisfaction with PT. MDT. The highest Customer Satisfaction Dimension of 4.58 is obtained according to Expectation Service (CS2). While the lowest Customer Satisfaction Dimension of 4.52 was obtained Repurchase Interest (CS3).

Table 6: T Test Results (Partial Test) Equation 1

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5,775	1,725		3,348	,002
	Corporate_Image	,697	,209	,693	3,422	,002
	Brand_Image	,224	,257	,159	,873	,387
	Harga	,585	,276	,400	2,121	,039

1) Corporate Image influences the Purchasing Decision

Based on table 6, it is known that Corporate Image has a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions. This is because Corporate Image has a t-count value of 3.422 > t-table value of 2.014 ($\alpha = 5\%$, $df = 45$) or with a significance value of 0,000 < 0,05, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So it can be concluded that the Corporate Image partially has a significant effect on the Purchase Decision.

2) Brand Image affects the Purchasing Decision

Based on table 6, it is known that Brand Image has no significant effect on Purchasing Decisions. This is because the Brand Image has a t-count value of 0.873 < t-table value of 2.014 ($\alpha = 5\%$, df

= 45) or with a significance value of $0.387 > 0.05$, then H_0 is accepted and H_1 is rejected. So it can be concluded that the Corporate Image partially has no significant effect on the Purchase Decision.

3) Prices affect the Purchase Decision

Based on table 6, it is known that Price has a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions. This is because the price has a t-count value of $2.121 > t$ -table value of 2.014 ($\alpha = 5\%$, $df = 45$) or with a significance value of $0.039 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So it can be concluded that prices partially have a significant effect on purchasing decisions.

Table 7: T Test Results (Partial Test) Equation 2

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3,162	,758		4,214	,002
Corporate_Image	,235	,084	,329	2,800	,008
Brand_Image	,320	,102	,317	3,136	,003
Harga	,255	,114	,244	2,240	,030
Keputusan_Pembelian	,287	,158	,221	2,492	,033

Source: SPSS 23 output, data processed

1) Corporate Image influences Customer Satisfaction

Based on table 7, it is known that Corporate Image has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. This is because Corporate Image has a t-count value of $2.800 > t$ -table value of 2.014 ($\alpha = 5\%$, $df = 45$) or with a significance value of $0.008 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So it can be concluded that the Corporate Image partially has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.

2) Brand Image affects customer satisfaction

Based on table 7, it is known that Brand Image has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. This is because the Brand Image has a t-count value of $3.136 > t$ -table value of 2.014 ($\alpha = 5\%$, $df = 45$) or with a significance value of $0.003 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So it can be concluded that Brand Image partially has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.

3) Prices affect customer satisfaction

Based on table 7, it is known that Price has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. This is because the Brand Image has a t-count value of $2.240 > t$ -table value of 2.014 ($\alpha = 5\%$, $df = 45$) or with a significance value of $0.030 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So it can be concluded that Prices partially have a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.

4) Purchasing Decisions affect customer satisfaction

Based on table 7, it is known that the Purchase Decision has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. This is because the Purchase Decision has a t-count value of $2.492 > t$ -table value of 2.014 ($\alpha = 5\%$, $df = 45$) or with a significance value of $0.033 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So it can be concluded that the Purchasing Decision partially has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.

Table-8: Structure Equation Table

Model	Standardized Coefficient Beta	t	Sig	R ²
PersamaanStruktur 1 (X ₁ , X ₂ , X ₃ terhadap Y ₁)				
X ₁ = P1 X ₁ Y ₁	0,693	3,422	0,002	0,673
X ₂ = P2 X ₂ Y ₁	0,159	0,873	0,387	
X ₃ = P3 X ₃ Y ₁	0,400	2,121	0,039	
PersamaanStruktur 2 (X ₁ , X ₂ , X ₃ , Y ₁ terhadap Y ₂)				
X ₁ = P4 X ₁ Y ₂	0,329	2,800	0,008	0,903
X ₂ = P5 X ₂ Y ₂	0,317	3,136	0,003	
X ₃ = P6 X ₃ Y ₂	0,244	2,240	0,030	
Y ₁ = P7 Y ₁ Y ₂	0,221	2,492	0,033	

Based on table 8, the following is an explanation of this study:

- 1) Analysis of the Effect of Corporate Image on Purchasing Decisions has a sig value of 0.002 <0.05 so it can be concluded that Corporate Image has a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions
- 2) Analysis of the Effect of Brand Image on Purchasing Decisions has a sig value of 0.387 > 0.05 so it can be concluded that Brand Image does not have a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions
- 3) Price Influence Analysis of Purchasing Decisions has a sig value of 0.039 <0.05 so that it can be concluded that Prices have a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions
- 4) Analysis of the Effect of Purchasing Decisions on Customer Satisfaction has a sig value of 0.033 <0.05 so it can be concluded that the Purchase Decision has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction
- 5) Analysis of the effect of Corporate Image on Customer Satisfaction through a Purchasing Decision. It is known that the direct effect of Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction is 0.329 while the non-significant effect of Product Quality on Customer Satisfaction through Purchasing Decisions is the multiplication of beta X₁ to Y₁ value with beta Y₁ to Y₂ which is 0.693 x 0.221 = 0.153. Then the total influence given X₁ to Y₂ is a direct effect coupled with an indirect effect which is 0.329 + 0.153 = 0.482.
- 6) Purchasing Decision is able to mediate the influence of Corporate Image on Customer Satisfaction. This is because the coefficient of determination (R²) equation 2 is 0.903 > coefficient of determination (R²) equation 1 is 0.673. So that it can be concluded that Corporate Image has an indirect effect on Customer Satisfaction through Purchasing Decisions

Corporate Image influences the Purchase Decision

Based on the results of the study, it is known that Corporate Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions. Corporate image is considered important for every company because it is an overall impression that is formed in the minds of the public about the company. The image can be related to the name of the business, architecture, variations of the product, tradition, ideology and impression on the quality of communication which is the interaction between consumers and the company. Image as an impression obtained according to one's knowledge and experience of something. Image is formed based on impressions, based on experience experienced by someone towards something to make a decision. The company is expected to communicate clearly about how the company meets the needs and needs of the

customer-oriented market so that it can lead the public to positively image the company. So that if the company image is positive, it will influence more positive purchasing decisions. The results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Saad and Ahmad that Corporate Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions.

Brand Image affects the Purchasing Decision

The results of the study show that Brand Image does not have a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions. This shows that the customer's perception of the products owned by PT. MDT is not a major consideration for customers. With the reputation of the company which was founded in 1960 and has operated in 370 locations in 160 countries, PT. MDT is highly trusted by customers without doubting the quality of their products. The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Sulistiyanto that Brand Image has no significant effect on Purchasing Decisions.

Price affects the Purchase Decision

The results of the study indicate that the price has a positive and significant effect on the Purchasing Decision. Prices are basically the basic theory of the marketing mix and consumer behavior. Both can be used when looking at prices for the purchase decision of a product or service product. Price has an important role in the decision making process, namely the role of price allocation is to help buyers to obtain products or services with the best benefits based on the strength of their purchasing power. Before deciding to buy a product or service, consumers will perceive whether the price of a product or service is affordable with a cheap price or a discount (promo) or a bonus (merchandise). After that, the new consumer decides the purchasing decision on a product or service. So, if low prices or high discounts will affect the increase in purchasing decisions. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Foster that Price has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions [18].

Purchasing Decisions affect Customer Satisfaction

The results showed that the Purchase Decision had a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is the feeling of likes or dislikes of a product after comparing the performance of the product with the expected one. In making purchasing decisions, consumers will only buy products of good quality. Consumers will experience a level of satisfaction if the goods obtained are in accordance with their needs and desires. Conversely, consumers will have dissatisfaction after making a purchase if the goods are not genuine, the needs are not in line with expectations, not in accordance with the promotion, and so on. The results of this study are in line with previous studies conducted by Suryonaningih, et al. Which showed that Purchasing Decisions had a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction [19].

Corporate Image influences the Purchase Decision and Its Implications on Customer Satisfaction
The results of the study indicate that Corporate Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions and their implications for Customer Satisfaction. Marketing strategies to increase the need for Corporate Image / company image are important, because Corporate Image is the identifier of the product offered. With the aim of improving the competitive position of a product or service that is in the form of retaining existing customers and capturing new customers. Company image is a psychological impression and a description of various activities of a company in the eyes of its public audience based on the knowledge, responses and experiences that have been received. Through purchasing decisions that have been made before, customers can assess

and evaluate company performance. The evaluation results will make customers satisfied with a company or vice versa. The results of these studies are in line with previous research conducted by Ene and Betül that Corporate Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions and their implications for Customer Satisfaction. (Should not exceed 10 pages)

The results section should provide details of all of the experiments that are required to support the conclusions of the paper. The section may be divided into subsections, each with a concise subheading.

It is advised that this section be written in past tense. It is a good idea to rely on charts, graphs, and tables to present the information. This way, the author is not tempted to discuss any conclusions derived from the study. The charts, graphs, and table should be clearly labeled and should include captions that outline the results without drawing any conclusions. A description of statistical tests as it relates to the results should be included.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research obtained, the following are the conclusions in this study.

- 1) The results of the study show that the Corporate Image has a positive and significant effect on the Purchase Decision.
- 2) The results of the study show that Brand Image does not have a significant effect on Purchasing Decisions.
- 3) The results of the study indicate that the price has a positive and significant effect on the Purchasing Decision.
- 4) The results of the study show that the Purchase Decision has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction
- 5) The results of the study indicate that Corporate Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions and their implications for Customer Satisfaction.

Suggestion

Based on the conclusions above, the following are the suggestions proposed in this study.

- 1) Based on the results of the study, it is known that Corporate Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions. In the variable dimension test, it is known that the Reputation dimension (CI2) has an outer loading value of 0.908. This shows that the reputation of the company is a consideration for customers to buy health products from PT. MDT. therefore, it is recommended that companies communicate more about the company's performance and achievements through the use of social media and websites that are informative for customers.
- 2) Based on the results of the study, it is known that Brand Image has no significant effect on Purchasing Decisions. In the variable dimension test, it is known that the Psychosocial Implication (BI3) dimension has an outer loading value of 0.931. Therefore, it is recommended that PT. MDT conducts training for hospitals to improve the skills of health workers in using medical devices.
- 3) Based on the results of the study, it is known that the Price has a positive and significant effect on the Purchase Decision. In the variable dimension test, it is known that the

Affordability dimension of the Price has an outer loading value of 0.900. Therefore, it is recommended that PT. MDT adds a number of bonuses such as price discounts for customers who have re-purchased PT. MDT

It is recommended that further research use other variables that influence purchasing decisions such as Personal Selling and others. It was intended to get more comprehensive research results.

References

- [1] Wijaya, Cynthia Violita. 2017. "Pengaruh Harga, Kualitas Pelayanan dan Kualitas Produk terhadap Kepuasan Konsumen Depot Madiun Masakan Khas Bu Rudy". *Jurnal Agora*. Vol. 5 No. 1.
- [2] Bayuningsari, Aprilia dan Barata, Dion Dewa. 2017. "Pengaruh Harga, Kualitas Produk, Promosi, Dan Citra Perusahaan Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan PT Bando Indonesia KeTurki Pada Periode 2009-2013". *Jurnal Bisnis Dan Komunikasi*. Vol. 4 No.2.
- [3] Hasanuddin, Makmur. 2016. "Analisis Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan, Lokasi Dan Harga Terhadap Kepuasan Nasabah Melalui Keputusan Pembelian Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Penjualan Logam Mulia Emas". *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*. Vol. 4, No. 1.
- [4] Saad, Norizan Mat and Ahmad Zulhaimi Bin Abdul Wahid. 2017. "The Influence of Store Image and Corporate Image on Customer Satisfaction: A Study in Petrol Station's Convenience Store Patronage in Malaysia". *Management International Conference*
- [5] Ene, Selda and Betül Özkaya. 2014. "A Study on Corporate Image, Customer Satisfaction and Brand Loyalty in the Context of Retail Stores". *Asian Social Science*. Vol. 10 No. 14.
- [6] Schiffman, L., and Kanuk, L.L. 2010. *Consumer Behavior*. 10th Edition. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [7] Kotler, Philip and Gary Armstrong. 2012. *Marketing Management*. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [8] Hawkins, Del.I., Roger J. Best., and Kenneth A. Conney. 2007. *Consumer Behaviour: Building Marketing Strategy*. Eight Edition. New Jersey: McGraw-Hill
- [9] Warren, Keagan. 2007. *Manajemen Pemasaran Global*. Jilid Kedua. Jakarta: PT. Macanan Jaya Cemerlang.
- [10] Lovelock, Christopher and Jochen Wirtz. 2011. *Service Marketing: People, Technology, Strategy*. Seventh Edition. New Jersey: Pearson.
- [11] Zeithaml, V.A., and Gremler, D.E. 2009. *Services Marketing: Integrating Customer Focus Across the Firm*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [12] Jefkins, Frank., dan Daniel Yadin. 2007. *Public Relations*. Edisi Kelima. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [13] Sulistyari, Ikanita Novirina. 2012. "Analisis Pengaruh Citra Merek, Kualitas Produk, dan Hargaterhadap Minat Beli Produk Oriflame". Tesis. Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- [14] Supranto, J. Dan Nandan Limakrisna. 2011. *Perilaku Konsumen*. Jakarta: Mitra Wacana Media.
- [15] Alma, B. 2014. *Manajemen Pemasaran dan Pemasaran Jasa*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- [16] Swastha, Basu. 2009. *Manajemen Penjualan*. Edisi 3. Yogyakarta: BPF.
- [17] Harini. 2008. *Makroekonomi Pengantar*. Jakarta: PT GramediaPustaka Utama
- [18] Foster, Bob. 2016. "The Effect of Price and Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in Mutiara Hotel Bandung". *American Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*. Vol. 12.
- [19] Sulistiyanto, F.X. 2015. "Pengaruh Persepsi Harga, Citra Perusahaan, dan Citra Merek terhadap Kepuasan dan Loyalitas Pelanggan pada Apotek "Dela" di Semarang". *Prosiding Seminar Nasional & Call for Paper*.

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